

THE CONTENT OF TEACHING YOUNG GENERATION TO NATIONAL CRAFTSMANSHIP IN TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The main topic of the article is to provide information about national crafts to the younger generation in technological education, and based on this, views and opinions on the essence of teaching them to national crafts.*

Keywords: *technological education, national crafts, training in national crafts, culture, cultural heritage, historical traditions.*

In our country, which is rapidly developing due to national independence, it is one of the urgent tasks to raise the level of education of the young generation to meet the requirements of world standards, to be aware of scientific and technical innovations, to be able to think independently, to enter life boldly, to be entrepreneurs, and to be spiritually mature. This, first of all, requires the improvement of every subject, educational system based on modern technologies.

It is possible to imagine the future of our country depending on the knowledge of the growing young generation and what kind of profession they will acquire in the future. Youth is the criterion of our prosperous life. Educating young people is the sacred duty of every parent, teacher-educator before the Motherland.

The transition to new economic relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan required a review of the current criteria of the general secondary education system and its modernization. The actual structure and organization of general secondary education should not be allowed to clash with the modern demands of the individual, society, and labor market, to separate education from the individual and to hinder production, economy, and social development. For this reason, it is important to interest and train students in fields such as folk crafts in technological education even in general secondary education.

Providing students in general secondary education institutions with sufficient knowledge, skills and qualifications for their chosen professions is closely related to the level of methodological preparation of teachers of vocational education being trained in higher education institutions. The main task of the teacher and master of vocational education is the professional training of students in professional educational institutions and general secondary educational institutions in their fields. On this basis, meaningful organization of practical training on technological education in schools, in which better development of students' knowledge, skills and abilities, especially improvement of their interest in national handicrafts, and for this purpose, introduction of various innovative lessons In the future, it contributes to the training of skilled craftsmen or young people who are interested in this field and organize additional work.

PF-5242 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - "On the further development of handicrafts and comprehensive support of craftsmen" also fully preserves and

increases the rich cultural heritage and historical traditions of our people, further development of national handicrafts, folk art and applied art, implementation of targeted and comprehensive measures for comprehensive support of citizens engaged in handicraft activities, on this basis, the population, especially young people, women and less In order to ensure the employment of well-off families, a number of tasks to be performed in the field of crafts have been defined.

The relevance of the topic of the article is related to the problems of the modern era and the educational trends of the 21st century, the key of which is not only the practice-oriented training of future craftsmen, but also independent in the field of traditional folk crafts and arts. formation and development of the experience of scientific-research activity was considered as an important condition for preservation, restoration and development of cultural heritage.

For this reason, the purpose of this work is to inform about the theory of traditional artistic crafts as a factor of improving the learning activity of the student at the age of acquiring a trade. In this case, the goal defines the tasks as follows:

- determining the place of the specified practical lesson processes in the continuous specialized professional education system in the field of traditional arts and crafts;
- determining the main dominants of the content of learning;
- to form its mission in the professional training of future masters, i.e. artisans, and more broadly, in ensuring the organic existence of traditional folk crafts in the 21st century.

The theoretical importance is to identify the dominants in the development of the content of practical lessons, which are included as fundamental lessons in the theory of traditional folk crafts, and their study and understanding become the main foundation for improving students' skills. Its role, content development process, features, organizational-pedagogical conditions, educational-methodological support features have become the topic reflected several times in the researches of the author of the article, in a number of articles published on the basis of the results of the research. it is worth noting.

An important feature of the training of high school students in the field of national crafts is the priority of activities aimed at enriching the graduate's professional capital with new qualities. Among them - the ability to develop a strategy of one's practical work, to implement it step by step and to reflect later; it should be taken into account that such factors as the skills of interaction with the professional community will also exist. With this, it is possible to achieve a wide opening of the doors of students' interests and aspiration to national handicrafts. All this is reflected in the expansion and improvement of the types of professional activities mentioned in the state educational standard (compared to the level suitable for high school students). The change in priorities for training masters of traditional art and national crafts in the upper class of general education is the reason for revising the content of professional theoretical and practical lessons for training future craftsmen. Or the methodology of traditional art and national crafts, it should be noted that deep attention should be paid to modern problems of traditional national crafts in Uzbekistan.

Also, in this process, it is also interesting to analyze the features of the content of traditional national craft theory classes in the practice of training future masters in national craft art secondary schools. First of all, the theory of national craft presents the following to students: its purpose is to form an understanding of the essence of the historical development, emergence and genesis of the main theoretical concepts in the field of national craft, as a condition for its scientific study at the current stage. Lessons aimed at forming ideas about the conditions and stages of the formation

of the theory of national handicrafts, as well as the organization of specialized classes in this direction, practical exercises designed to acquire the skills of national handicrafts in students for this purpose helps to achieve Acquaintance with the set of tasks for handicraftsmen, which motivates them to carry out their scientific research in the field of national handicrafts of our country, also motivates students to be partially aware of the difficulties and achievements of national handicrafts.

It should also be noted that an important feature of classes devoted to the theory of national crafts is the transition from reproductive activities (lectures) to productive activities (practical training and independent extracurricular activities) in the development of its content, which is also in the upper class. it corresponds to the specific characteristics of the study, as well as to the priorities of the modern education policy in general. Therefore, the scientific research activity that dominates the mastery of the theory and methodology of national handicrafts will improve the students' functional literacy skills, gain experience in conducting independent theoretical research in this direction in the future, express their opinion and express their own point of view. serves to directly discuss his point of view.

It is noted that craft activities are based on historically settled special knowledge, skills, secrets, methods of the people, using manual labor, tools and small mechanized means, based on traditional and modern requirements, domestic, is a type of creative or professional activity in the production (service), preparation of household, artistic items. Informing today's youth, especially high school students, about this will lead to the preparation of artisans who will actively participate in the sustainable development of this industry in the future.

Nowadays, it is necessary to prepare young people to acquire entrepreneurial skills, to teach them knowledge of small business and entrepreneurship in modern conditions. Another important factor in maintaining a stable environment in educational institutions is today's labor education. It is impossible to maintain stability in education and family without labor education. Basically, close and distant relatives of this family, neighbors, surrounding people and neighborhood people play a big role as social factors that influence the life values of the child in family upbringing. It is very important for them to be able to guide the child's behavior correctly, to show the child the right path without breaking his values, to guide and encourage the child correctly. is of great importance. Because the right attitude to the profession is one of the ancient values of the Uzbek people. For this reason, family and school cooperation is important in arousing the interest of the young generation in national handicrafts. This will increase efficiency.

In conclusion, it can be said that all of the above mentioned one after the other serves to arouse the interest of the young generation in national handicrafts and to encourage them to be active in these processes. Therefore, it is necessary to pay close attention to the content and essence of teaching the young generation to national crafts in technological education, to organize practical processes with the help of innovative technologies, to inform students about the achievements of national crafts on a global scale, every practical training Emphasis on national crafts during training is the basis for increasing respect, interest and attention to national crafts among the younger generation.

REFERENCES

1. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
2. Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova. ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF TECHNOLOGY IN PREPARING PUPILS FOR EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF FOLK CRAFTS. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 100-101p.
3. Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova. METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF COMPETENCES OF PUPILS' INTEREST IN NATIONAL CRAFTS BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 MARCH 2023. 373-374p.
4. Roila Yuldoshevna Xaydarova. CLUSTER TYPES AND ORGANIZATION OF THE PROCESSES OF LESSONS DEDICATED TO NATIONAL CRAFTS FROM TECHNOLOGY SCIENCE BASED ON THEM. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 MARCH 2023. 68-69p.
5. Roila Yuldoshevna Xaydarova. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CLUSTER APPROACH IN MODERN EDUCATION. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 1 JANUARY 2023. 434-435p.
6. Шаповалова И.А. Научно-исследовательская деятельность как ресурс развития творчества будущих художников в области традиционного прикладного искусства и народных промыслов. *Традиционное прикладное искусство и образование*. 2019; No 3 (29): 43 – 51. Available at: http://dpio.ru/stat/2019_3/2019-03-05.pdf
7. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
8. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman
9. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
10. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman
11. <https://cyberleninka.ru>
12. <http://scientists.uz>
13. <https://www.bukhari.uz>